

Product Recommendations Using Collaborative Filtering

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Abstract ----- A vast number of products are now acquired on the internet. Proper product suggestion to users for purchase is a critical aspect in maintaining customers interest in using the online shopping platform. Product recommender engines are now commonly employed in e-commerce sites. A suggestion is made based on a variety of factors, such as categorically related goods, the most often purchased products, user behaviour-based recommendations, ratings and review-based recommendations, and so on. The recommender that's proposed here follows review based collaborative filtering using k-nearest neighbours and cosine similarity.

Keywords—recommender, collaborative filtering, cosine similarity, k-nearest neighbors.

I. INTRODUCTION

This is being implemented to make recommendations to users of items that may be of interest to them. Receiving strong suggestions exposes the user to new and varied items, increasing the probability of the user making a purchase.

The preferences of users are established by the ratings they provide to purchased items. The ratings of all purchased goods given by a single user are picked, and comparable rating patterns of other users are detected using cosine similarity and the k-neighbours method.

This pattern predicts the user's ratings for non-purchased items, and non-purchased products with the highest expected ratings are recommended to that user. This method of using users behaviour for personalized recommendation is called Collaborative filtering.

Collaborative filtering is highly suited to the use of personalised recommendations. The foundation of a collaborative filtering system is a history of individual preferences. Similarity is determined by the overlap of tastes; people who enjoy the same things are similar [1].

Furthermore, votes are weighted by distances, therefore the votes of closer neighbors are considered more important, in other words, it is an approach for discovering any items that fits into the current preferences of a specific person based on suggestions of a peer group chosen for their same tastes. This method is also known as social information filtering. Collaborative filtering automates the process of relying on word of mouth to predict whether or not they will enjoy anything. Knowing that a large number of people enjoyed something is insufficient. Even if you don't usually buy a business's product, the recommendation of a close friend whose prior recommendations have been spot on may be enough to get you to purchase a specific product from that

company, ie, recommendation is not depending on products popularity but users behaviour. [2]

Basic steps of the procedure:

- Data Preparation:
- Collaborative Filtering
- Recommendation and Calculated Rating

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Le Nguyen Hoai Nam proposed a memory-based collaborative filtering to predict items as expected by users. It comprises two phases: calculating the preference similarity between each pair of users in the offline phase, and predicting an active user's rating for a target in the online phase.. Published 5 January 2022 [3].

Jia Xuefeng constructed an electric project knowledge graph through the project abstract and CNKI database. Then, uses semantic and collaborative similarity to find the experts most relevant to the project. Finally, discussions on the outperformance and conditions of the proposed model and compared the recommendation results with state-of-the-art methods. Published 1 March 2022. [4]

Yi-Chin Cho, Chiao-Ting Chen and Szu Hao-Huang proposed a graphical deep collaborative filtering (GraphDCF) algorithm for providing personalized mutual fund recommendations. In a sequential perspective, the graph-structured network is built by linking client nodes with related purchases and redeemed trade orders. We may construct distinct latent associations among clients with comparable buying behaviours in this way. Published on 22 December 2021. [5]

Elsevier B.V proposed a review based recommendation system that use collaborative filtering method. This system deals with rating's sparsity problem by implementing matrix factorization technique and increase accuracy of the recommender. Published on 3 February 2022. [6]

For a movie dataset, Neha Shrivastava and Surendra Gupta investigate both user and item based collaborative filtering recommendation algorithms. The findings show how well

both strategies work and which one produces the greatest results. Published on 11 December 2021. [7]

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this system is to recommend products to the different users based on interest of previous purchases by evaluating the ratings, they give for the purchased products and evaluating similar rating patterns.

Main steps.

- Data Collection and Preparation.
- Collaborative Filtering
- Recommendation
- Result Analyzing

Data Collection and Data Preparation:

Data which include id of user, id of product, product title and ratings can be collected from either ratings.csv files or from database. With all of the existing users and available products, a data-frame pivot table is constructed. The value of the pivot table is based on the ratings each user provided for each product. The products for which the user has not given a rating are given value of 0.

```
import pandas as pd
r = pd.read_csv('a.csv', usecols=['userId', 'productId', 'rating'])
products = pd.read_csv('products.csv', usecols=['productId', 'title'])
r2 = pd.merge(r, products, how='inner', on='productId')
df = r2.pivot_table(index='title', columns='userId', values='rating').fillna(0)
```

Figure: 1

Code to create dataframes of products and ratings. The dataframes are then combined to form a single dataframe on products. Pivot table is constructed using this merged dataframe.

userId	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
title											
gillette 7'o clock	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
acer nitro 5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
acer predator helious	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
apsara pencil	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
asus rog strix g17	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
camlin instrument box	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
camlin notebook	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
cinthol	4.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
classmates notebook	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
closeup max fresh	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
colgate maxfresh	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0
dazler	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0
hp notebook	0.0	0.0	5.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0
iphone series x	2.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
lifeboy sanitizer	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Figure : 2

Above is the image of pivot table created with product name as index, user id as columns and ratings given as values.

Pandas — Pandas is extremely useful when working with datasets and dataframes. Pandas is an open source python library which is an and easy to use data analysis and manipulation tool.

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Figure 1

Figure: 3

The frequency of ratings from the pivot table is shown with a pie chart. The pie chart's header values are ratings, which range from 1 to 5, with 0 denoting no rating. The proportion of each rating out of the overall rating is shown in each section.

Collaborative Filtering

NearestNeighbors is used to discover the most comparable product for each product and determine the distance between them using cosine similarity. Ratings given by users is the basis of identifying product similarity.

Nearest Neighbors – The KNN algorithm is a supervised machine learning approach for solving classification and prediction problems. The KNN algorithm predicts the values of new datapoints based on 'feature similarity,' which means that a value will be assigned to the new data point based on how closely it resembles the points in the training set. [8]

```
knn = NearestNeighbors(metric='cosine', algorithm='brute')
knn.fit(df.values)
product_distances, product_indexes = knn.kneighbors(df.values, n_neighbors=3)
```

Figure : 4 The image contains the code which uses knn and cosine similarity to fit the dataframe values into a model and find the nearest neighbors as product_indexes and distance from them as product_distances.

Cosine Similarity

Cosine similarity is a metric used to compare measure the similarity of two vectors. It evaluates the similarity of the vectors' direction or orientation, ignoring differences in their magnitude or scale. Both vectors must be in the same inner product space, which means that they must create a scalar via inner product multiplication. The cosine of the angle between two vectors is used to determine their similarity.[9]

The algorithm of this recommendation engine is as follows:

Step 1:

Calculate similarity between products using KNN. The similarities are determined using all of the user ratings.

Step 2:

For each product a user hasn't rated, predict the rating:

Find closest products based on the similarity calculated in the Step 1.

For the closest products, calculate the weighted average of the ratings by the user. The weight is calculated using the inverse distance metric.

Use the weighted average of the ratings as the predicted rating for the product by the user.

Step 3:

Recommend products which have the highest predicted ratings for the user.

Predicting the Ratings

The formula to calculate the predicted rating is as follows:

$$\hat{A}_{pu} = \frac{\sum_r A_{ru} B_{pr}}{\sum_r B_{pr}}$$

Where \hat{A}_{pu} is the predicted rating for product p by user u, A_{ru} is the actual rating for product r by user u and B_{pr} is the similarity between product p and product r.

The projected rating for a product is just the weighted average of ratings for similar goods, according to this

formula. The weight for each rating, $\frac{B_{pr}}{\sum_k B_{pk}}$, becomes greater when product p and product r are more similar. The denominator of this term makes the sum of all the weights in \hat{A}_{pu} become 1.

Product Recommendations:

- Once the predicted rating for non purchased products are identified, the products with the highest predicted rating is recommended to that particular user.
- If a consumer updates ratings for a product they has purchased, the recommended items are changed to reflect the updated ratings.

Result Analysis:

```

Enter user id
4

Choose:

1. Recommendation
2. View Ratings
3. Change Ratings
4. Rate new Product
1
Number of products to be recommended
4
The list of the Products 4 user Bought

apsara pencil
classmates notebook
hp notebook

The list of the Recommended Products

1: velva - predicted rating:5.000000000000001
2: acer nitro 5 - predicted rating:5.0
3: acer predator helious - predicted rating:5.0
4: asus rog strix g17 - predicted rating:5.0
    
```

Figure : 5 - Userid = 4

Products User 4 has rated are listed.

No of recommendation = 4 (user input)

Based on product similarity, 4 products are recommended to the user along with calculated predicted ratings by the user.

```

Enter user id
4

Choose:

1. Recommendation
2. View Ratings
3. Change Ratings
4. Rate new Product
3
Products 4 bought :

ProductId Name
19 apsara pencil Rating : 1
18 classmates notebook Rating : 5
10 hp notebook Rating : 5

Enter product id to change ratings
10

Ratings to change out of 5
1

Rating successfully changed
    
```

Figure : 6 - User id = 4

All products User 4 rated are listed along with given ratings. User is going to change product 10- HP Notebook ratings from 5 to 1.

```

Enter user id
4

Choose:

1. Recommendation
2. View Ratings
3. Change Ratings
4. Rate new Product
2

Products 4 bought :

ProductId Name

19    apsara pencil Rating : 1
18    classmates notebook Rating : 5
10    hp notebook Rating : 1
    
```

Figure : 7

If you check the rating change, product 10-- Hp notebook now has Rating = 1 updated by User 4.

```

Enter user id
4

Choose:

1. Recommendation
2. View Ratings
3. Change Ratings
4. Rate new Product
1

Number of products to be recommended
4

The list of the Products 4 user Bought

apsara pencil
classmates notebook
hp notebook

The list of the Recommended Products

1: iphone series x - predicted rating:2.386184825822112
2: scobby - predicted rating:2.386184825822117
3: acer nitro 5 - predicted rating:1.0
4: acer predator helious - predicted rating:1.0
    
```

Figure : 8 - For User 4, we can see that, the current recommended products are different from previous recommendation for User 4.

It's because user 4 changed ratings for one of the products, Hp notebook from 5 to 1.

This changed the current recommendations and predicted ratings accordingly for user 4.

```

Enter user id
12

Choose:

1. Recommendation
2. View Ratings
3. Change Ratings
4. Rate new Product
1

Number of products to be recommended
3

The list of the Products 12 user Bought

gillette 7'o clock
acer predator helious
asus rog strix g17
iphone series x
lifeboy sanitizer

The list of the Recommended Products

1: apsara pencil - predicted rating:5.0
2: camlin instrument box - predicted rating:5.0
3: camlin notebook - predicted rating:5.0
    
```

Figure : 9 - Recommendation for different user.

User id = 12

No of recommendation = 3

We can see that different users are getting different recommendation of products and its based on rating pattern of each users.

IV. CONCLUSION

Collaborative Filtering act as a substitute for user's word of mouth for products within the site itself. A recommendation system based on collaborative filtering is an attractive feature for any ecommerce system.

Good product recommendations can attract customers attention to new products which he may be interested in purchasing. This overall increases customers curiosity and satisfaction about the shopping site, allows them to browse and purchase more products and increase sales.

V. REFERENCES

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